

Serbia's ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Reforms in the research sector

- Increase of GERD to €520 million and 0.99% of GDP (2021)
- Promotion of research excellence
- Further development of the national innovation system through institutional reforms (e.g. Science Fund)
- Improvement of transnational cooperation
- Increase of number of Open Access publications due to an improved Open Science Policy
- Construction of four Science and Technology Parks

Development of deep-tech system

- New Law on Digital Assets (2020)
- Further growth of blockchain technologies
- Tax incentives for start-ups and high-tech companies
- Establishment of an Institute for Artificial Intelligence (2021)
- Ensurance of sustainable investments in major national R&I projects through building long-lasting public-private partnerships

Gender equality

- New Law on Gender Equality aligned with the EU acquis (2021)
- 42.6% female graduates with STEM degrees (2020)
- 52.3% female researchers (2021)

Very good participation in EU Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation

- Most active of the Western Balkans economies (e.g. ANTARES Teaming for Excellence project)
- Proposal success rate higher than EU Member States' average
- Steady increase of participation and Net EU contribution since Framework Programme 4

Recommendations

Internationalisation activities

- Promote international research mobility
- Support competitive scientific projects with international collaborations
- Encourage researchers and institutions to participate in European scientific associations and organisations
- Pursue cooperation agreements with EU Member States in science and technology
- Intensify participation in macro-regional strategies
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings and engage in the new European Innovation Agenda

Support application oriented research

- Further promote recently introduced R&D tax incentives to increase business sector's investment in R&D
- Improve cooperation between science and industry to support programmes for technology transfer

Increase activities in R&D policy making

- Increase implementation efficiency of R&D strategic policy documents and action plans and ensure their ongoing monitoring and evaluation
- Update regulations for the evaluation of scientific research to encourage researchers to apply for patents
- Introduce concrete measures to increase the share of women in top-level positions in the R&D sector

Further develop research infrastructure

- Increase memberships in current and new activities of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
- Support researchers' experiences in high-level research projects with respect to research infrastructures
- Establish a new National Research Infrastructure Roadmap

